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Geomorphodiversity index of Switzerland for multiscale analysis

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Abstract— Geodiversity refers to the variety of Earth's physical features and processes, and it represents the geosphere counterpart of biodiversity. The abiotic diversity supports natural processes and sustains biotic niches, and it contributes to the human health through a wide range of ecosystem services. Geomorphodiversity, as a part of geodiversity, describes the diversity of landforms, resulting from the lithological and surface processes modelling the landscape. Combining information from a geo-lithological map and quantities derived from a digital elevation model with a simple, multi-scale and reproducible approach, results in discrete geomorphodiversity index (GmI). The raster index has an intuitive content and can be represented at different spatial resolutions, depending on input data and purpose of the study. Here, we implemented the method to obtain the first geomorphodiversity map of Switzerland. The map nicely represents the landscape variability of Switzerland and it can be valuable to identify areas at national scale with a potential hazard for natural phenomena (landslides, flooding, and others). As the index aims at representing the abundance and diversity of landforms in an area, we compared GmI with a field-based geomorphological dataset of the Hérens valley, in Southern Switzerland. The local-scale assessment shows that GmI is an additional tool to understand surface diversity from large- to local-scale, for land use management, and to promote the conservation of natural areas in a broad sense.

I. INTRODUCTION

Geodiversity is “the natural range (diversity) of geological (rocks, minerals, fossils), geomorphological (landforms, processes) and soil features” [1] and is widely recognized as the “silent counterpart” of biodiversity. It supports the natural

processes occurring in the ecosystems and human health, through a wide range of ecosystem services [2,3].

Urban sprawl and induced landscape modifications alter the stability of natural ecosystems [4]. The vast majority of the scientific literature and the nature-based solutions focus on biodiversity protection, overlooking the role of the abiotic richness of Earth surface, or geodiversity [5]. Monitoring the heterogeneity and the evolution of the Earth surface and sub-surface abiotic features [6] act as indicators of areas with a high degree of naturalness, enhancing their protection and promoting conservation strategies.

Several different methods exist in the literature to study geodiversity, each with different assumptions and aims [7,8]. Geomorphodiversity specifically considers landforms, their abundance, their diversity, and the morphogenetic processes modelling the landscape. Moreover, geomorphodiversity is a one of the components of ecosystems, and geomorphodiversity mapping may help geoconservation actions and delimiting Natural Protected Areas [9].

One of the challenges for the assessment and mapping of geomorphodiversity is the definition of proper spatial and temporal scales [10]. Selecting proper spatial scale is essential for including geodiversity as an environmental input if ecological models, to model species distributions, and draw conclusions about conservation strategies [11].

The quantitative index defined by [12] represents geomorphodiversity as the variety of features and the

morphogenetic processes modeling the landscape [13], and lithological information [14, 15], combining high resolution elevation data, geology, and digital elevation model (DEM)-derived data, through simple and repeatable steps. [16] improved on the method, including a multi-scale approach. Here, the method is applied to obtain a GmI raster map of Switzerland. Despite its limited area, Switzerland is characterized by a high variety of geomorphological features [17] resulting from the combination of endogenous and exogenous factors, like the multiple lithotypes, the geological evolution, mainly marked by the Alpine orogeny, and the climatic diversity, due to its peculiar geographical location, at the interface between Northern Europe and the Mediterranean area. These conditions result in diverse landscape types, which are borne out in the proposed GmI. The map provides information about the geomorphological diversity in five classes, which constitutes the abiotic framework and the resources for natural and human development, land management, biodiversity conservation and natural resource management, as well as geoheritage selection and geotourism management.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Assessment of the GmI for Switzerland, at a national scale, required the following input data.

1. The Copernicus EU-DEM, a raster layer supplied by the European Environmental Agency (EEA, available at <https://www.eea.europa.eu/>). The horizontal resolution is of 25 m and the vertical accuracy is of 2.9 m. We used this data for the assessment of (i) the slope angle and (ii) the derived terrain forms.
2. A map of the geological complexes of Switzerland at 1:500,000 scale, a vector layer supplied by the Federal Office of Topography swisstopo and describing 25 different lithotypes across Switzerland.
3. The swissTLMRegio dataset, supplied by the Swiss Federal Office of Topography swisstopo, providing river network

information. It contains high quality and homogeneous information, with accuracy between 20 m and 60 m.

4. The map of the main geomorphological landscapes at 1:500,000 scale, in a vector format, published in the Atlas of Switzerland in 1975 and providing an overall picture of the four main morphogenetic landscape types of Switzerland: glacial, fluvial, karstic and gravitational. The dataset does not correspond to a field-based geomorphological map, but shows information concerning the most relevant geomorphological agents influencing the landforms variability.

The original approach of [12] adopted a raster resolution of 500 m for the GmI map. In this work, we fully exploited the EU-DEM 25 m resolution and obtained a GmI with the same spatial resolution, and we followed the multi-scale approach by [16, 18]. Moreover, we introduced a more flexible method to combine the partial diversities of each input quantity into the final GmI map. In fact, in previous as well as in this work, we first calculated diversity maps of individual input quantities. With diversity, we mean the number of different classes of each input quantity within a given neighborhood; their combination represents the final GmI result. We considered four raster surface descriptors, namely, DEM-derived slope angle and landforms (terrain patterns), drainage network, and lithological information. Figure 1 outlines the procedure adopted in this work, described in detail in the following.

The slope angle is a relevant factor for the heterogeneity of lands, since it affects the erosion, transport and accumulation processes that determine the denudation of the bedrock. Landforms are an essential feature entering the geomorphological variability in an area. We considered the geomorphons model by [19], which is suitable for large areas and automatically detects up to ten land surface patterns: flat, peak, ridge, shoulder, spur, slope, hollow, foot slope, valley, and pit. We considered such method as a close approximation to landforms existing in the field. The drainage density map allows investigating the

Fig. 1. The workflow leading to the high-resolution geomorphodiversity map (GmI) of Switzerland. From left to right, the different panels illustrate the actions described in Section II. (1) input data, (2) parametric calculation of partial diversity using moving windows, (3) combination of partial maps into as many GmI maps as the values of the parameter R (moving window radius), representing (4) an ensemble, scale-dependent geomorphodiversity assessment, and (5) scale-independent assessment of GmI selecting cell-by-cell most common value of the index across the ensemble. The core of the method is in step (b), corresponding to the assessment of partial diversities, i.e., the calculation of diversity of each input descriptor. Here, by diversity we mean the number of different values within the neighborhood singled out by a circular moving window of given size.

Fig. 2. The land surface diversity index, or geomorphodiversity index (GmI) of Switzerland, obtained in this work. The index is provided in five classes, from 1 (lowest diversity class) to 5 (highest diversity class). In the figure, the raster map is resampled at 500 m resolution, for easy reading; the actual result of this work has 25 m spatial resolution.

morphogenetic processes that occur in fluvial areas and in alluvial plains, where other topographic features, as the slope angle, are mostly uniform and less meaningful using DEMs with a medium horizontal resolution and vertical accuracy. Lastly, we considered the lithological map supplied by the regional Switzerland dataset. The lithological characteristics of a territory are significant information since they affect the response to the exogenous agents and geomorphological evolution of the surface over time.

The first step (Fig. 1(b)) was to calculate four partial diversity grid maps, one for each input raster map (slope, landforms, drainage density and lithology), with a moving window (focal statistic) GIS operator. To get a multi-scale result, we repeated the operation several times, with circular moving windows of radius varying between 11 and 91 grid cells, with grid size 25 m. We ended up with nine different diversity maps for each input quantity and we classified each map in five diversity levels, using Jenks breaks, a data-driven classification method (Fig. 1(c)).

Each group of four partial diversities, calculated with moving windows of the same size, collapses into one preliminary and scale-dependent (moving window radius-dependent) GmI map, by a combination procedure (Fig. 1(d)). In the case of Switzerland, availability of a national geomorphological overview map allowed us to perform a combination of partial diversities with a weighted sum, followed by final classification, using weights to reflect the main morphogenetic landscape units: glacial, fluvial, karstic and gravitational. The geomorphological characteristics of the primary processes in each physiographic unit helped selecting meaningful values of the weight.

We consider that in karstic, glacial and gravitational landscapes, hydrography has a minor impact as a modelling agent. In the karst, most of rivers disappear underground and slopes are

not steep, so drainage density is less relevant. In the glacial environment, water discharge is poorly channelized and in the gravitational unit most of the landforms are due to erosion, heavy rains or snow melt. On the contrary, where the fluvial landscape has a crucial role, in particular on wide alluvial plains, the river network represents the most significant modeling agent while the topographic attributes are less meaningful due to the low angle slope values. Use of a weighted sum allowed extra flexibility in reproducing the diversity of landforms in the different geomorphological settings of Switzerland, where specific modeling agents are prevalent.

Eventually, we obtained a final scale-independent GmI map, out of the nine scale-dependent maps, overlaying them and selecting in each grid cell the most common value across the spectrum of nine different geomorphodiversity values using the option “mode” in GIS raster calculator (Fig. 1(e)). This allowed us to remove GIS processing artifacts, and to obtain a parameter-free approach to GmI assessment.

III. RESULTS

We calculated the GmI map of Switzerland, obtained by weighted combination of the partial diversities of slope angle, drainage density, geomorphons and lithology, classified in five classes; Figure 2 shows the full map.

Areas with GmI = 1, the lowest class, represent 6.68 % of Switzerland and prevails in the karst environment, with sparsely scattered areas. Class 2 covers 28.21 %, which is homogeneously distributed in the four geomorphological environments. The medium geomorphodiversity, class 3, represents 24.67 % and it is prevalent in the glacial (31.33 %), gravitational (33.14 %) and fluvial (32.48 %) environments, whereas the class is less represented in the karst (22.01 %). Class 4 covers 28.07 % of the total surface; the largest distribution is in the fluvial environments, 30.87 %, followed by the gravitational ones, 28.13 %, the glacial ones, 23.68 %, and the karst, 10.96 %. The GmI 5 class represents 12.39 % of the country. It is slightly prevalent in the fluvial environments (13.88 %), followed by the gravitational (11.76 %) and the glacial (10.69 %) ones. The karst is the landscape with the lowest percentage of the highest class, corresponding to 2.26 %.

IV. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

This work proposes the first geomorphodiversity index map for Switzerland, through a quantitative approach. The basics of the method were inspired by [12] and [16], who described surface diversity of Italy combining raster variability maps of slope, landforms, drainage density and lithology. The final GmI map, in five categories, includes information from these four inputs and represents an intuitive assessment of abiotic diversity in Switzerland.

With respect to previous work, we further exploited an additional data layer that identifies glacial, gravitational,

periglacial and karst landscapes, depending on the main geomorphological processes. Hence, we introduced a weighted approach for partial diversity maps, matching the numerical weights to the geomorphological characteristics of the primary processes in each landscape unit.

In the GmI map, the highest values of diversity are in the fluvial and gravitational environments, followed by glacial contexts. Abundant rivers and channels shape these landscapes, and the lithological complexity represents different endogenous assumptions for the geomorphic agents. Within our approach, the lowest value of GmI is the less represented across the country, and is mostly found in the karstic areas, as expected. In the karst landscapes, altitude resembles that of the fluvial landscapes, and the climatic setting is quite uniform. These parameters affect the processes shaping the landscapes, and their characteristics are compatible with a low surface diversity. The reasons for a lower geomorphodiversity in the karst environment may reside on (i) high permeability and (ii) low drainage density. The karstic landscape, at the scale and in the climatic environment considered in this study, features a gentler topographic surface than areas where glacial and gravitational processes prevail.

The method applied here is versatile, in both the number and type of surface descriptors involved, as well as the resolution of the output GmI map. It includes contributions calculated at different spatial scales, relevant for large areas assessment as well as for local studies. Moreover, it considers different classes of landforms, automatically extracted from the DEM – which gives extra information without the need to resort to manual and subjective terrain classification. Use of specific morphological units (valley, ridges, peaks, and other classes included in this work) was shown to be crucial to add explanatory power in ecological modeling, along with hydrology, soil, and geology information [11].

We acknowledge that an assessment of geomorphodiversity accounting for the spatial distribution of surface descriptors, in addition to the number of different values, would likely change the results presented here. Implementation of the procedure described here into a software module in GRASS GIS is underway.

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